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**(Chloro) bis(π -methylcyclopentadienyl)-
N-Aryldithiocarbamato Zirconium(IV)
Complexes**

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In earlier communications¹⁻⁴, we reported a number of organometallic compounds involving dithiocarbamate ligands. Our interest in the investigation of bonding mode of the dithiocarbamate groups, prompted us to synthesise and characterise a number of (chloro) bis(π -methylcyclopentadienyl)-N-aryldithiocarbamato zirconium(IV) complexes. IR spectral studies indicate that the dithiocarbamate group is bidentate in these complexes.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets using Perkin Elmer grating spectrophotometer, Model 621. Electronic spectra were run on a Perkin Elmer 4000A instrument. Conductance measurements were made on a Beckmann conductivity bridge, Model RC-18A. Magnetic measurements were made by Gouy's method, using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobaltate(II) as the calibrant.

Ammonium salts of dithiocarbamic acids were prepared by the method of Klopping and Kerk⁵. (π -CH₃C₅H₄)₂ZrCl₂ was prepared by the reaction of zirconium tetrachloride and bis(methylcyclopentadiene) in THF⁶. Nitrobenzene was purified for

conductance measurements by the method described by Fay *et al*⁷. Zirconium, nitrogen and sulphur were estimated by standard methods⁸.

All the complexes were prepared by a similar method. A solution of (π -CH₃C₅H₄)₂ZrCl₂ was refluxed with calculated amounts of ammonium dithiocarbamates for 12-14 hr. The contents were filtered while hot and the filtrate concentrated under vacuum at room temp. Petroleum ether (60-80°) was added to the concentrated filtrate and the mixture was allowed to stand overnight. The products were obtained as white or pale yellow crystals. These were filtered, washed with petroleum ether and recrystallised from an acetone solution by the addition of petroleum ether.

Results and Discussion

The reaction of (π -CH₃C₅H₄)₂ZrCl₂ with ammonium salts of dithiocarbamic acids may be represented by the following general equation

The complexes are white or pale yellow in colour. They are thermally quite stable. The compounds are soluble in THF, DMSO and acetone and partially soluble in halogenated hydrocarbons. Conductance measurements show that all the complexes are essentially non-electrolytes in nitrobenzene. Magnetic susceptibility measurements at room temp. indicate that the complexes are diamagnetic. The electronic spectra exhibit a single broad band in the 27750-24250 cm⁻¹ region. This is assigned to the charge transfer band⁹, similar to that exhibited by the complexes having the metal ions in (n-1)d⁰ns⁰ electronic configuration. The analytical data and physical characteristics of the complexes are listed in Table 1.

Whether the dithiocarbamate group is monodentate or bidentate is reflected in the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ stretching frequency. The 980-1050 cm⁻¹ region is associated with the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ stretching frequency. The presence of only one strong band in this region supports the bidentate behaviour of the dithiocarbamates, whereas the appearance of a doublet in this region indicates one complexed (C-S) group and one uncomplexed (C=S) group, that is monodentate bonding^{10,11}. The present complexes exhibit only a single absorption band at ~1000 cm⁻¹ which supports the bidentate and chelating nature of the dithiocarbamate ligand in all the cases.

The thioureide group, S=C-N, in case of dithiocarbamate complexes absorbs at ~1500 cm⁻¹^{12,13}. The frequency of this band lies intermediate to the C-N bond (1200-1300 cm⁻¹) and the C=N (1650-1700 cm⁻¹) stretching vibrations. In the present complexes, the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretching frequency absorbs in the range 1380-1420 cm⁻¹. The occurrence of this band at a lower energy as

NOTES

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA AND PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Compound (π -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄) ₂ Zr(S ₂ CNHR)Cl	Conductance $\Lambda^{(1)}$ ($0.5 \times 10^{-3} M$)	Zr	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)		
			Cl	S	N
R=phenyl	0.26	20.10 (20.15)	7.72 (7.84)	14.19 (14.10)	3.00 (3.09)
R= <i>o</i> -tolyl	0.27	19.65 (19.54)	7.69 (7.61)	13.60 (13.71)	3.10 (3.00)
R= <i>m</i> -tolyl	0.26	19.63 (19.54)	7.50 (7.61)	13.80 (13.71)	3.01 (3.00)
R= <i>p</i> -tolyl	0.24	19.44 (19.54)	7.69 (7.61)	13.62 (13.71)	3.03 (3.00)
R= <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl	0.27	18.81 (18.90)	7.25 (7.35)	13.20 (13.26)	2.99 (2.90)
R= <i>o</i> -ethoxyphenyl	0.27	18.28 (18.36)	7.02 (7.15)	12.76 (12.88)	2.84 (2.92)
R= <i>p</i> -ethoxyphenyl	0.25	18.45 (18.36)	7.06 (7.15)	12.80 (12.88)	2.76 (2.82)
R= <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl	0.28	18.64 (18.72)	14.47 (14.57)	13.08 (13.14)	2.78 (2.87)
R= <i>m</i> -chlorophenyl	0.26	18.63 (18.72)	14.68 (14.57)	13.21 (13.14)	2.96 (2.87)
R= <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	0.30	18.80 (18.72)	14.43 (14.57)	13.25 (13.14)	2.78 (2.87)
R= <i>p</i> -bromophenyl	0.32	17.25 (17.16)	—	12.10 (12.04)	2.70 (2.63)
R= <i>p</i> -iodophenyl	0.27	15.66 (15.77)	—	11.01 (11.06)	2.31 (2.42)

(1) in $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$

compared to the metal dialkyldithiocarbamate complexes^{1,4} indicated considerably low double bond character of the (C=N) bond in these complexes. The magnitude of the drift of electrons towards the sulphur atom in metal dithiocarbamates depends on the nature of groups attached to the nitrogen. In dialkyldithiocarbamates, there is a drift of electrons towards the sulphur atoms, due to the presence of electron releasing alkyl groups. Thus the (C=N) bond has appreciable double bond character in such cases. However, the replacement of alkyl groups by electron withdrawing aryl group(s) weakens the drift of electrons towards the sulphur atoms, making the double bond formation of the (C=N) bond considerably less as compared to the dialkyl dithiocarbamate complexes. Thus, the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretching is observed at a lower frequency.

In the far ir region, the bands appearing at $\sim 350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to the $\nu(\text{M}-\text{S})$ stretching frequency^{1,4} and the bands at $\sim 375 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region to the $\nu(\text{M}-\text{Cl})$ stretching vibrations^{1,5}.

The proton chemical shifts (δ scale) for the protons of the cyclopentadienyl ring show a broad singlet around 5.8.

The CH₃ group in π -CH₃C₆H₄ moiety shows a resonance signal at 2.2. The signals for the aromatic groups in the dithiocarbamate moieties are observed in the expected frequency regions. The intensities of the signals were determined by planimetric integration and the results of the integrated proton ratios correspond to the formula (π -CH₃-C₆H₄)₂Zr(S₂CNHR)Cl.

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